

Current approaches to minimize the late blowing defect of cheese

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ABSTRACT

The late blowing defect (LBD) is an issue in semi-hard and hard cheeses, as once the phenomenon occurs, it is impossible to amend and affects large production volumes. Therefore, it is a matter of major economic importance for cheese processors resulting in significant losses. This defect is characterized by the cracks formation and unpleasant flavors due to butyric fermentation. Several *Clostridium* spp. have been characterized as responsible bacteria, but *C. tyrobutyricum* is the microorganism most commonly isolated from affected cheeses. This is because it is more salt-tolerant than other species and it can grow suitably at typical ripening temperatures used in cheesemaking. Several attempts have been made to establish the minimal spore number required to cause LBD. Still, it is a complicated task because it depends on the microbial strain, cheese, and the method used for quantifying the bacterial load. Several different studies have been conducted to prevent the occurrence of cheese LBD. Some are directed to minimize the contamination of milk in the farm, others are aimed to remove the spores through physical methods and a third strategy consists of implementing sporestatic or sporicidal procedures. In this work, these approaches are discussed.

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1. Introduction

Although some defects of cheese are due to poor cheesemaking practices (rennet failure, lack of hygiene, unsatisfactory salinity, inadequate water activity, etc.), most spoilage threats of cheese have a microbial origin. Microorganisms can enter milk via udder, air, feedstuffs, milk-handling equipment, etc. Besides the sanitation during milking, pasteurization effectively reduces the common bacterial load, extending the shelf life. Nevertheless, after processing, a variety of organisms may reach the cheese from the environment or the industry facilities. The growth of undesirable molds or bacteria on the cheese can alter the surface of the pieces such as abnormal colorations, presence of mycelium, or slime formation. The interior of the cheese is a hostile medium for many organisms due to unfavorable water activity (a_w), pH, and low oxygen tension (Eh). Additionally, products of lactate fermentation, combined with the moisture and salt levels and good hygiene, effectively limit the range of bacteria that can produce gas in cheese (Mullan, 1986). However,

some bacteria can grow if the medium conditions allow it, leading to defects that compromise quality and result in economic losses.

The blowing of cheese, caused by unwanted bacteria, is perhaps the major risk of spoilage in cheesemaking. Cheese production without blowing remains yet a challenge for the dairy industry. Depending on the time this defect takes to appear, two types of blowing can generally be distinguished: early and late gas defects. The origin of each is different.

The early swelling of cheese is characterized by the appearance of numerous small and irregular holes in the first few days of ripening due to the gas (carbon dioxide and hydrogen) generated, mainly, by coliforms (Fox et al., 2017). The presence of these bacteria in cheese is typically due to the use of poor hygienic quality milk. Early gas production may also result from the presence of high levels of gas-producing, non-starter (heterofermentative) lactic acid bacteria in the cheese (Mullan, 2000; Sheehan, 2022). Currently, this problem is rare if appropriate hygiene practices are followed during milking and

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cheese manufacture, milk pasteurization (the responsible organisms are killed by this thermal treatment), avoiding post-pasteurization contamination, and the use of active starter cultures (Sheehan, 2022). In the present work, the early gas production is left aside, and only the late blowing defect is addressed.

2. The late blowing defect (LBD)

The LBD becomes evident from 4 to 6 weeks after cheese manufacture to several months into cheese ripening (D'Amico, 2017; Düsterhöft et al., 2017; Düsterhöft & Van den Berg, 2007). Various bacteria can cause this defect, e.g. heterofermentative lactic acid bacteria (LAB), such as *Lactobacillus brevis* and *Lactobacillus fermentum* (currently *Levilactobacillus brevis* and *Limosilactobacillus fermentum*, respectively), which generate lactic acid and CO₂ through the phosphoketolase pathway (Wang et al., 2021). The defect has also been observed in Emmental cheese due to the decarboxylation of aspartic acid, which produces alanine and CO₂, facilitated by the action of L-aspartate-4-decarboxylase found in certain propionibacteria strains (Fröhlich-Wyder & Bachmann, 2007). Similarly, the aforementioned species can decarboxylate certain free amino acids once the lactose is depleted and produce slits while yielding the corresponding amine and CO₂. However, LBD is generally associated with the butyric acid bacteria (BAB) of the genus *Clostridium* which can produce butyric and acetic acids, carbon dioxide, and hydrogen through the utilization of the copious lactate resulting from lactic acid fermentation (O'Sullivan et al., 2013; Sheehan, 2022). The main species involved in the LBD are *C. butyricum* and *C. tyrobutyricum* being later the dominant causative species (Alvenas, 2015; Brändle et al., 2018; Hill & Kethireddipalli, 2013; Morandi et al., 2021). The brined cheeses are particularly susceptible to LBD because the salt can take time to migrate to the interior of cheese and is therefore unable to limit the growth of *C. tyrobutyricum* at initial phases of ripening. For these reasons, and since it is more salt tolerant than other BAB, this species has been presented as the primary cause of cheese LBD in multiple studies (D'Incecco et al., 2018; Garde et al., 2011; Klijn et al., 1995; Qian et al., 2022) although other species have also been isolated from LBD cheeses, such as *C. beijerinckii* (Le Bourhis et al., 2007), *C. sporogenes* (Morandi et al., 2021) and, recently, the new species *C. jeddahense* (Kaya et al., 2023).

Cheeses likely to present LBD are rennet coagulated and surface salted. Examples include semi-hard cheeses like both Dutch Gouda and Edam (Walstra et al., 1999),

as well as Spanish Manchego (Garde et al., 2011). As well as hard cheeses with characteristic "eyes" like Swiss Gruyère and Emmental (Daly et al., 2010), along with hard Italian Grana types (Gobbetti, 2004), are also susceptible to LBD. From 2g of lactic acid, 1g of butyric acid, and 1000mL of gas (mixture of CO₂ and H₂) are formed during butyric fermentation (Fröhlich-Wyder & Bachmann, 2007). Because of the impermeable and elastic character of the body, these gases become trapped and expanded, leading to blowing accompanied by irregular holes and cracks and, eventually, the rupture of the cheese piece. Hydrogen, with very low solubility in the aqueous phase, greatly contributes to this swelling phenomenon (Daly et al., 2010). The accumulation of butyric acid (Bergère & Favreau, 1987) and acetic acid (Fröhlich-Wyder & Bachmann, 2007) during the process leads to the development of undesirable off-odors and off-flavors.

Both L-lactate presence and acid pH in the cheese paste promote the outgrowth of *Clostridium* spores (Bassi et al., 2009). When favorable environmental conditions occur (pH, Eh, a_w , etc.) during the cheese ripening, the spores of BAB can germinate into vegetative cells. Subsequently, the vegetative cells grow inside the piece, and the LBD appears within a few weeks if the a_w does not reach inhibitory levels for clostridia (McSweeney & Fox, 2004). They are very sensitive to the a_w and minimum values of 0.96 and 0.956 have been reported for *C. butyricum* (Ghoddusi et al., 2013) and *C. tyrobutyricum* (Huchet et al., 1995), respectively. These a_w values are typical in several semi-hard and hard cheeses with moisture and NaCl contents (g/100g) of 35–37 and 3–6, respectively, such as Gouda, Gruyère, Emmental, Cheddar, Appenzeller, Manchego (Guinee & Fox, 2017; Marcos et al., 1981). Nevertheless, it must be taken into account that in the first weeks of ripening, when the microorganisms that cause LBD begin to multiply, the cheeses have a_w values greater than 0.96, and they decrease thereafter mainly due to the progressive salt diffusion and moisture loss. For example, the a_w of the hard cheese Los Pedroches shows at the beginning of ripening (2d) a value of 0.979, decreasing then to 0.974 in the following 7d, achieving a value of 0.962 and 0.953 in 22 and 43d, respectively (Sanjuán et al., 2002), the latter can be considered an inhibitory level for the growth of *C. tyrobutyricum*. Similarly, in Gouda cheese, a salt concentration of 3.0% of dry matter (equivalent to 1.95g per 100g of cheese with 35% moisture) is enough to prevent the germination of clostridia (Düsterhöft & Van den Berg, 2007). In this cheese type, the salting process is made by immersion in brine and the salt progressively diffuses from the rind to the

interior, reaching that concentration about 8 weeks after manufacturing, providing sufficient time for LBD to occur (Düsterhöft & Van den Berg, 2007). In contrast, Cheddar cheese undergoes a more uniform salt distribution throughout the mass, as the salting is achieved by mixing the salt with the curd grains before pressing, which explains why LBD is less frequent in the latter variety (McSweeney & Fox, 2004) supported additionally by a lower pH compared to other cheeses susceptible to develop LBD such as Edam, Emmental, Gruyere, Parma (Marcos et al., 1981).

The cooking of the curd is another feature that may influence the appearance of the LBD. It has been observed in Grana Padano cheese that vegetative cells of *C. tyrobutyricum* are killed when the curd is cooked at 54°C but if a residual population of spores withstands, they could germinate and multiply afterward and, consequently, the LBD may occur at later stages (D'Incecco et al., 2018).

3. Butyric acid bacteria (BAB)

BAB belong to cluster I of the large and heterogeneous genus *Clostridium*, referred to as *Clostridium sensu stricto* according to the revised taxonomic status of this genus (Cruz-Morales et al., 2019), in which the species *C. sporogenes*, *C. beijerinckii*, *C. butyricum* and *C. tyrobutyricum* are included. The BAB have been isolated, alone or in association, in cheeses with obvious signs of LBD (Bacci et al., 2002; Bassi et al., 2015; Cocolin et al., 2004; Garde et al., 2011; Le Bourhis et al., 2005; Matteuzzi et al., 1977). Although *C. tyrobutyricum* is generally considered the major causative agent of this defect, the role played by other species cannot be underestimated. For example, in Grana Padano cheese, *C. butyricum* begins to grow at the beginning of ripening when lactose is still available, and the pH is not too acidic. In more advanced stages of ripening, when the level of acidity is higher, *C. tyrobutyricum*, an acid-tolerant species, actively multiplies (Driehuis, 2013) and effectively utilizes lactate (Driehuis, 2013; Gobetti & Di Cagno, 2007). Likewise, it has been observed in Emmental cheese (Le Bourhis et al., 2007) that the development of *C. tyrobutyricum* at early stages of ripening may have resulted in conditions stimulating germination, increasing the multiplication of *C. sporogenes* and *C. beijerinckii*. In addition, acetate and amino acids issued from the metabolism of the two later species favor the growth of *C. tyrobutyricum* (Bergère & Hermier, 1970). Similarly, it has been also found ecological associations between some strains of LAB (*Streptococcus thermophilus* and lactobacilli and BAB.

For example, cheeses characterized by a high abundance of *S. thermophilus* and *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* (currently *Lactiplantibacillus rhamnosus*) were spoiled by *C. tyrobutyricum* whereas when *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* was the most abundant, *C. butyricum* was the dominant spoiling species (Bassi et al., 2015). Likewise, the growth and acid formation of species of *Clostridium* are promoted when grown with some bacteria, such as *Streptococcus* spp., *Leuconostoc* spp., lactobacilli, propionibacteria, etc (Gómez-Torres et al., 2014; Hunter & Frazier, 1961).

4. Approaches to control the LBD

Studies conducted in recent decades show the presence of BAB in milk tanks intended for cheese manufacturing at levels above 50% (Coulon et al., 1991; Turchi et al., 2016; Zucali et al., 2015) and, in some cases, even close to 100% (Feligini et al., 2014; Garde et al., 2011). Table 1 shows typical concentrations of BAB spores reported in milk from different mammalian species. As spores are resistant to pasteurization (Ingham et al., 1998), they pass into the curd and cheese where they subsequently germinate. Additionally, the brines used in the salting stage can be another potential source of contamination, as surviving spores can readily pass into them, accumulating over time since brines are often reused (Su & Ingham, 2000).

Over the years, intensive research has been performed to develop suitable culture methods for determining the milk contamination level by clostridia. Nevertheless, the results are still unsatisfactory as the existing methods are time-consuming and inaccurate (Brändle et al., 2016), and information is often based on personnel experience (Burtscher et al., 2020). However, some authors have offered data in this respect. It has been claimed that one *C. tyrobutyricum* spore/mL in milk is enough to cause the LBD in hard cheeses (Fryer & Halligan, 1976), even it has been recommended that milk used for manufacturing Gouda cheese should contain fewer than one *C. tyrobutyricum* spore per 10mL (Klijjn et al., 1995). Borreani et al. (Borreani et al., 2019)

Table 1. Typical levels of butyric acid bacteria (BAB) spores in tanks of raw milk from different species.

Milk Type	Log spores/L	References
Cow	1.79–3.63	(Borreani et al., 2019; Brändle et al., 2018; Burtscher et al., 2023; Coulon et al., 1991; Su & Ingham, 2000)
Sheep	2.56–5.38	(Klijjn et al., 1995; Salmerón et al., 2002; Scintu et al., 2004; Shi et al., 2023; Zucali et al., 2015)
Goat	2.40–3.70	(Arias et al., 2013)

divided the spore numbers that could lead to the onset of LBD in the hard cheese-making process into three classes: <2.3 (low), 2.3–3.0 (medium), and >3.0 (high probability) log most probable number (MPN)/L, respectively, although the threshold values may depend on the cheese type being produced and the MPN-based count methods. However, a recent study (Carminati et al., 2023) suggests that a low level of BAB spores in vat milk (<log 2.3/L) could prevent or limit the onset of LBD in Grana-type and similar cheeses. The mentioned levels are lower than the typical spore load usually reported (Table 1). Nevertheless, the former figure may not be sufficient to avoid the LBD in cheeses produced in the warm season since the milk contains a higher number of spores (Carminati et al., 2023; Garde et al., 2011). On the other hand, the development of LBD depends on the *C. tyrobutyricum* strain present (Podrzaj et al., 2020).

Different measures have been devised to minimize the BAB load in both milk and cheese. Some actions are directed at preventing milk contamination on the farm, while others aim to remove the spores from raw milk using physical methods. A third type of measure consists of implementing sporestatic or sporicidal procedures to avoid the growth of butyric bacteria in cheese. These strategies are discussed below.

4.1. Actions to prevent milk contamination on the farm

Clostridia are part of the soil microbiota, so they often reach plants that feed livestock. After the animals digest this feed, the spores concentration in the feces is 3–10-fold higher than that ingested with food (Stadhouders & Jørgensen, 1990). These spores can then transfer directly from the feces to the udder or pass through the cattle bedding, ultimately contaminating the milk during the milking process (Burtscher et al., 2023; Heyndrickx, 2011). Recently, a study was conducted on the effect of teat cleaning on the number of spores in milk, concluding that, on average, routine pre-milking teat cleaning resulted in a reduction of 0.6 log units (76.2% reduction). These authors also found that the average cow cleanliness correlated strongly with butyric acid producing clostridia spore levels in milk, suggesting the potential for a quick and rough estimation method of clostridial contamination of milk. Therefore, the number of BAB in milk is closely linked to the hygienic practices applied on the farm. In some countries, the clostridia spores count has been used as a quality marker for milk intended for cheese production. Thus, economic sanctions have been imposed on farms when the

cow milk contains a spore count exceeding, e.g., 10^3 spores/L (Demarquilly, 2020; Vissers et al., 2007) or 1.3×10^3 sp/L in sheep and goat milk (Pirisi et al., 2007). Alternatively, cheese milk should contain 10^4 cfu/mL to be classified as Grade A milk according to FDA (Alvenas, 2015; FDA, 2024).

Since spores are mainly carried in feces, the feed received by cattle is directly correlated with the occurrence of *Clostridium* spp. in milk. In this context, ensilage emerges as the primary source of contamination and, consequently, the spore number is proportional to the percentage of silage consumed by the animal (Coulon et al., 1991). To prevent spore contamination, certain cheeses, including Emmental, Gruyere, and Parmigiano Reggiano, are not allowed to be produced from milk obtained from cattle fed with silage (Demarquilly, 2020; Di Cagno et al., 2001). The silage process acceleration is another procedure to minimize the spore load in the milk, which can be achieved by selecting a vegetal material with a higher carbohydrate content than that of proteins (Driehuis & Elferink, 2000). Other approaches have also been proposed to prevent BAB proliferation in the silage process, including reducing the a_w by adding dry matter (Wieringa, 1958), generating nitrites and nitric oxide through nitrate degradation (Van den Berg et al., 2004), and using biologically active LAB starter cultures to inhibit Gram-positive bacteria (Gómez-Torres et al., 2014; Martínez-Cuesta et al., 2010).

4.2. Removal BAB spores from raw milk via physical methods

While the clostridial spores causative of LBD are not strongly heat-resistant, they withstand the high-temperature-short-time (HTST) pasteurization applied to milk intended for cheese making (Ingham et al., 1998; Sheehan, 2022). This treatment is not feasible for reducing spore numbers due to the reported D-values (time at a given temperature to kill 90% of the population) at 85 °C of 23 min (at pH 7), 14–21 min (in milk) and 30–47 min (in milk) for *C. beijerinckii* (Brown, 1990), *C. butyricum* (Cerf et al., 1967) and *C. tyrobutyricum* (Cerf et al., 1967), respectively. Assuming a z value = 10 °C, the D-value at 75 °C would be, in the most favorable case (*C. butyricum*), about 280 min, which is far from the usual conditions of HTST milk pasteurization (72 °C, 15 s). To reduce the clostridial spores count to suitable levels for preventing the LBD occurrence, a more severe heat treatment than HTST would be necessary, capable of achieving at least 4–5 decimal reductions of the original spores load. According to the thermal

parameters mentioned above (D85°C value 30–47 min, $z=10^{\circ}\text{C}$), a flash treatment of 10 seconds at 115°C would be satisfactory to reach that goal. However, the application of this treatment is unfeasible due to the inability to achieve a proper curd formation for cheese production, caused by changes in mineral balance and, more important, the denaturation of whey proteins, mainly α -lactalbumin (α -La) and β -lactoglobulin (β -Lg). With heat, β -Lg unfolds and exposes previously masked sulfhydryl groups and hydrophobic areas of the peptide chain. This exposed sites can then interact with other whey proteins and κ -casein to form aggregates, primarily β -Lg- β -Lg, β -Lg- α -La, β -Lg- κ -casein and β -Lg- α -La- κ -casein (Goulding et al., 2019; Wijayanti et al., 2014) which adversely affects milk coagulation mediated by rennet. Thus, it is necessary to explore other technologies, namely bacto-fugation and microfiltration.

4.2.1. Bactofugation

Bactofugation, involving centrifugal force at about 10,000g, has been tested to remove spores from milk. The process was developed by Simonart and De Beer in the early 1950s (Simonart & Beer, 1953). Although originally intended to be a method to increase the shelf-life of consumer milk, its most important application has proved to be in the cheese industry (Klantschitsch, 1999). The principle of bacto-fugation is based on the density difference between the milk (1.028–1.038g/ml) and the bacterial spores (1.30–1.32g/ml) (Gésan-Guiziou, 2010). The spores are settled in the pellet, containing 80%–90% of the total spores in the medium (Lembke & Teuber, 1981), although other authors (Lembke & Teuber, 1981; Waes & Heddeghem, 1990) have reported reductions in the range 86%–98%, which corresponds to a decimal reduction of 0.85 up to 1.7. Despite the reduction in spore numbers, viable spores may remain that can germinate and multiply in cheese making it impossible to ensure that LBD does not occur (Bylund, 2003). Double bacto-fugation can increase the reduction level to 99% or more, but it involves a higher investment (Gésan-Guiziou, 2010). During bacto-fugation, some milk components, particularly part of the caseins, are retained in the sludge (Bylund, 2003), which can lead to a lower cheese yield. However, this drawback may be solved by a subsequent UHT treatment (e.g. 130°C, 2–4s) of the sludge and recombined with the bacto-fuged milk afterward (Brändle et al., 2016; Guinee & O’Callaghan, 2010). In general, bacterial centrifugation alone seems to be insufficient to

prevent butyric acid fermentation but could be combined with the addition of 2.5g KNO_3 /100 liters centrifuged milk when clostridial spore levels before centrifugation are $\leq 6/\text{mL}$ (Waes & Heddeghem, 1990). Anyway, the initial level of spore concentration in milk and the temperature of ripening are very important factors. For example, a spore count in milk of <0.05 spore/mL could minimize the LBD (Qian et al., 2022). This is the case of Grana, Gruyère and Emmental cheeses, which can be produced from milk with BAB spores counts by centrifugation to ≤ 0.02 – 0.04 spores/mL of cheese milk (Waes & Heddeghem, 1990).

4.2.2. Microfiltration

Cross microfiltration involves liquid flowing tangentially through a membrane with a pore size of 0.2–1.4 μm under high pressure (0.05–0.2MPa) at 37°C–50°C (Bargeman, 2003; Sheehan, 2022). A 1.4 μm membrane means that larger particles will not pass through. The size of the spores of the BAB ranged between 1.5 and 3.0 μm , thus the spores remain concentrated in the retentate (Bargeman, 2003; Piot et al., 1987). Reductions of the 97.00%–99.98% of *C. tyrobutyricum* spores have been reported (Klantschitsch, 1999). However, this method is restricted to the removal of spores from skimmed milk, as it also retains fat globules with diameters ranging from 2 to 10 μm (Brändle et al., 2016) although the retentate (cream and spores) may undergo a high-temperature treatment, e.g., 115°C for 5–6seconds, and then be remixed with the permeate (Klantschitsch, 1999). A recent proposal suggests applying double homogenization of milk before microfiltration to reduce fat globule size to values lower than 1–2 μm (Leconte et al., 2014).

4.3. Sporestatic/sporicidal actions to avoid the growth of BAB in cheese

In addition to milk strategies to control LBD, various approaches can be taken during cheese manufacturing, namely the use of substances/ingredients to inhibit either the spore germination or growth of vegetative cells of *Clostridium* spp. or the application of proper physical technologies to kill spores and/or the vegetative cells. Several compounds have been assayed to control the clostridial cell growth, including nitrates, lysozyme, and antagonistic microorganisms even experimental studies have been carried out to explore the possibility of using aromatic plants (Librán et al., 2013).

4.3.1. Nitrates

The use of nitrates was one of the most preferred approaches in the cheese-making industry against the LBD due to its ease, cost-effectiveness, and safety (Klantschitsch, 1999). Its addition to milk intended for the manufacture of cheese at doses of 150 mg/liter of milk is authorized in the European Union, [Regulation (EU) 1129/2011], sufficient to avoid the germination of 10^4 spores/L (Düsterhöft & Van den Berg, 2007). However, in some countries, nitrates are not authorized (e.g. United States, Switzerland, Greece). For Swiss-type cheeses, a major drawback of this method is the inhibitory effect of nitrite on the growth of propionic acid bacteria since they are responsible for the characteristic eye formation, making nitrate use unsuitable for these cheeses (Beresford et al., 2001).

Throughout the ripening process, the nitrate-reducing organisms present in cheese, including lactobacilli and surface microbiota, along with the enzyme xanthine oxidase from the fat globule membrane actively reduce nitrate to nitrite. Nitrite is considered an inhibitor of spore outgrowth (Ávila et al., 2014; Brändle et al., 2016). However, as nitrate decomposition takes place, a portion of nitrogen is quickly washed out during brining and dissipates as gas. Spore germination is not fully inhibited but it is delayed until the salt concentration becomes homogeneous in the paste (Klantschitsch, 1999; Oliveira et al., 2016).

In addition to the mentioned drawback, another concern associated with the use of nitrates is the potential formation of nitrosamines. However, this risk is considered low since the pH required for this reaction is lower than that typically found in cheeses (Brändle et al., 2016). On the other hand, the degradation products of nitrite, namely nitric oxide, and nitrogen, evaporate as gas (Van den Berg et al., 2004). Studies on Dutch cheese have indicated that nitrosamine levels are either very low or even undetectable (Beresford et al., 2001). Nevertheless, the EFSA recommends minimizing the use of nitrites and nitrates as food additives to reduce the potential for nitrosamine formation (Beresford et al., 2001; Brändle et al., 2016).

4.3.2. Lysozyme

Lysozyme addition for the matured cheese production is allowed by Regulation (EU) 1129/2011, following the *quantum satis* principle, with a typical dose of 500 units/mL of milk (equivalent to 25 mg/L). The antimicrobial action of this enzyme lies in its ability to hydrolyze the β -1,4-glycosidic bond between N-acetylmuramic acid and N-acetylglucosamine of

the peptidoglycan of the cell wall of the Gram-positive bacteria (Zhang et al., 2014). As LAB belong to this group, its addition for the control of LBD requires the selection of the starter culture based on the susceptibility of the species and the dose of lysozyme added to milk (Klantschitsch, 1999). Nevertheless, it has been reported that a dose of 20 mg/L did not compromise the functionality of the most relevant lactic acid bacteria in Grana Padano cheese (D'Incecco et al., 2016). Since 90% of the enzyme is active during lactic fermentation, this procedure seems appropriate only for controlling LBD when the number of clostridial spores in milk is low, below 500 spores/L, but in the case of higher spore numbers, the application of lysozyme is not recommended (Brändle et al., 2016) because the higher doses required for higher spore numbers can inhibit the desirable lactic fermentation (Sheehan, 2022). On the other hand, the response of different clostridia spores involved in LBD to lysozyme is variable (Ávila et al., 2014; Bassi et al., 2015; Wasserfall & Teuber, 1979).

From a health perspective, a concern regarding the use of lysozyme is its source, as it is extracted from the egg white (Silvetti et al., 2017), which can trigger allergic reactions in sensitive individuals (European Food Safety Authority, 2014). Hence, it needs to be declared on the cheese label (EU regulation 1169/2011).

4.3.3. Antagonistic microorganisms

4.3.3.1. Microbial cultures. In addition to the environmental conditions, the growth of microorganisms is influenced by competition with other organisms present in the medium. Therefore, another possible strategy to control LBD is the addition of a culture able to inhibit *Clostridium* spp. This antibacterial action is attributed to metabolites released by the culture, with bacteriocins being the most relevant among them.

Bacteriocins are peptides with antimicrobial activity synthesized by bacteria. They are considered GRAS compounds since they are produced by LAB, naturally found in a wide of fermented products variety. Additionally, bacteriocins are easily degraded by enzymes in the intestinal tract of mammals (Silva et al., 2018). The mechanism of action and spectrum of activity of bacteriocins are diverse. Generally, their antagonistic action targets the cell membrane (Cotter et al., 2013) either by inhibiting the synthesis of peptidoglycan in Gram-positive bacteria (Breukink & de Kruijff, 2006) or by damaging cells through the formation of pores in the cell membrane (Egan et al., 2016). Nisin also exhibits a sporestatic effect by binding to sulfhydryl groups of protein residues

(Chen & Hoover, 2003). Others prevent the multiplication of bacteria by inhibiting gene expression (Parks et al., 2007; Vincent & Morero, 2009) or protein synthesis (Metlitskaya et al., 2006).

Nisin is the only bacteriocin authorized as a preservative by food regulations (e.g., EU Regulation 1129/2011 permits its use in matured and processed cheeses at doses of 12.5 mg/kg). Other bacteriocins are not authorized, so the alternative possibility is to incorporate the producer culture during the cheese-making process, allowing the release of the bacteriocin into the food matrix (Chen & Hoover, 2003). Various LAB species have been suggested to inhibit the germination of *Clostridium* spp. spores, including those producing bacteriocins such *Streptococcus macedonicus* (Anastasiou et al., 2009), *Lactobacillus plantarum* (González & Zárate, 2015), currently *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus reuteri* (Gómez-Torres et al., 2014), (currently *Limosilactobacillus reuteri*), *Lactobacillus gasseri* (Bogovič Matijašić et al., 2007) and *Streptococcus thermophilus* (Mathot et al., 2003), among others (Ávila et al., 2020; Hassan et al., 2021). It has also been observed that some yeasts exhibit antibacterial activity against *C. butyricum* and *C. tyrobutyricum* (e.g., *Debaryomyces hansenii* in Pecorino Romano cheese), apparently due to competition with clostridia for lactate and acetate (Deiana et al., 1984). Nisin-producing LAB are generally characterized by both weak lactic acid production and limited proteolytic activity, which is a technological limitation requiring the inclusion of a nisin-resistant starter culture (Brändle et al., 2016).

4.3.3.2. Lytic bacteriophages. The lytic phages offer great potential as biocontrol agents against undesirable microorganisms present in various foods. They attack bacterial cells, causing disruption and ultimately leading to cell death. Some studies have been made on phage addition to the milk to control both pathogenic and spoilage microorganisms in cheese. These investigations have been restricted to non-sporeforming bacteria, such as *Salmonella* Enteritidis (Modi et al., 2001), *Staphylococcus aureus* (El Haddad et al., 2016), *Escherichia coli* (Tabla et al., 2022) and *Enterococcus faecalis* (del Rio et al., 2019). However, recently, the activity of some phages isolated from milk against *C. tyrobutyricum* and their role in preventing LBD in cheese have been studied (Ávila et al., 2023). The authors concluded that good phage survival is detected during semi-hard cheese manufacture and ripening (60 d), and cheese lactococci counts, pH, dry matter values, and volatile compounds were not affected by the phage addition. A phage strain, FA67, impaired the early germination of *C. tyrobutyricum* spores and caused a significant decrease

in clostridial vegetative cell counts at 14 d of ripening, delaying by 2 weeks the consumption of lactic acid, the formation of butyric acid, and appearance of late blowing symptoms, compared to the spoiled control cheese without the phage.

This approach is a natural and low-cost technique, and its application may be interesting since the phages are highly host-specific and they do not affect either the sensory characteristics of the food or the damage equipment surface (Ramos-Vivas et al., 2021; Vikram et al., 2021). Furthermore, the phages have been described as safe for humans, and are inadvertently ingested through water and food (D'Amico, 2014).

4.3.4. Additional comments

A model (Monte Carlo simulation) has been recently developed to predict the occurrence of LBD in Gouda cheese and, through a what-if analysis (WIA), evaluate six intervention strategies to diminish it (Qian et al., 2022). As a reference, the average of the percent of LBD cheeses predicted by the model with the lower (log 2,38/L) and upper (log 2,45/L) *C. tyrobutyricum* spore concentration thresholds in raw milk was used, resulting in LBD occurrences in cheeses of 9.2%, 36.15% and 69.2% at 60, 90 and 120 d, respectively. Microfiltration and bactofugation (assuming a spore removal effectiveness of 98%) were the most effective methods, predicting no spoiled cheeses at 60 and 90 d of ripening, and a reduction in the LBD from 69.2% to 0.6% at 120 d. The 2.5% (w/v) sodium nitrate addition to milk and lowering the ripening temperature (from 13°C to 12°C) were the next most effective interventions, with an equal reduction (until 1.2%) in LBD at any ripening time for nitrate, and reductions from the reference percentages to 0.3%, 2.0%, and 6.3% for cheese ripening at 12°C. The behavior of the other three variables [use of premium milk (count of 25 spore/L compared to 143 spore/L of the reference), inoculation of a 24-hour nisin-producing *Lactococcus lactis* culture (0.3%), and addition of 2.5% (w/v) lysozyme to milk] differed substantially according to the ripening time. For example, at 120 d, reductions between 12.2% (lysozyme and *L. lactis* culture) and 41.8% (premium milk) were predicted. The authors report that the scarcity of data on *C. tyrobutyricum* growth in cheeses and the limited data on BAB subtypes and their ability to cause LBD represent limitations of the model. Despite the model was performed for Gouda cheese, the authors claim it provides a framework for developing a digital tool that can aid in mitigating the negative impact of LBD in several cheese types, although it would be necessary to add additional data as the LBD depends on several factors,

such as cheese type, pH, water activity, and time and temperature of ripening (Vikram et al., 2021). Interestingly, the implementation of bactofugation would have a profound impact in reducing LBD incidence since these approaches could prevent LBD during the first 90d of ripening. However, the 98% efficacy used to develop the model is higher than some published data, such as 80%–90% (Lembke & Teuber, 1981) and 86%–98% (Gésan-Guizou, 2010; Waes & Heddeghem, 1990). Double bactofugation could increase the reduction level to 99% or more (Gésan-Guizou, 2010). Microfiltration was assumed to have the same effect than bactofugation. This technology is more efficient than bactofugation since reductions of 99% or more have been reported (Klantschitsch, 1999). Nevertheless, this technology is less practical, as it can only effectively be used on skin milk (Brändle et al., 2016).

4.3.5. Physical technologies to eliminate *Clostridium* spp

4.3.5.1. High hydrostatic pressure (HHP). The application of HHP is a physical, non-thermal processing technology that can be used to inactivate certain microorganisms present in food. Pressures in the range of 200 up to 600MPa are commonly used in commercial food applications (Mota et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2016). It has primarily been applied in the food industry as post-packaging pasteurization to kill vegetative organisms (Georget et al., 2015). HHP is particularly useful for sanitizing ready-to-eat (RTE) foods lacking bactericidal steps in the production chain, as they cannot be treated by thermal processing once packaged. Indeed, HHP has been successfully applied to eliminate *Listeria monocytogenes* in various RTE products, including cold-smoked salmon (Gudbjornsdottir et al., 2010; Montiel et al., 2012), sliced cooked ham (Myers et al., 2013), sliced dry cured ham (Garriga et al., 2004), dry cured beef (Rubio et al., 2007), and cheese (Carminati et al., 2004; Shao et al., 2007).

At first glance, HHP seems to be a suitable procedure to be applied to hard and semi-hard cheeses since, according to the isostatic principle, pressure applied is transmitted instantaneously and uniformly throughout the food, regardless of size, shape, and composition (Martínez-Rodríguez et al., 2012). The application of HHP to cheese has been mainly focused on ripening acceleration to reduce production costs. For example, in Cheddar cheese, an increase in the proteolysis phenomena was observed, resulting in a much shorter ripening time (O'Reilly et al., 2003). The effectiveness of applying HHP to cheeses to eliminate *Clostridium* spp. spores has also been tested to control the LBD (Martínez-Rodríguez et al., 2012).

The results have not been highly relevant due to the significant resistance of spores although the HHP sporocidal effect may be improved if the treatment is applied in two cycles, with the first inducing spore germination and the second killing the vegetative cells (Georget et al., 2015). Nevertheless, other authors have observed that a single cycle of HHP at 300–500MPa for 10min at 14°C applied to ewe semi-hard cheese after 7d of ripening prevented the butyric acid fermentation caused by *C. tyrobutyricum*. The effect was not attributed to the clostridial spore inactivation but to the killing of emerged *C. tyrobutyricum* vegetative cells, which carry out the butyric fermentation thereby preventing the LBD presentation (Ávila et al., 2016). HHP also have a bactericidal effect on LAB. It has been reported that from a LAB load of approximately 8.0 log cfu/g, a reduction of 2–4D-values of mesophilic LAB was achieved through the application of 500MPa in both Hispanic (Munir & Federighi, 2020) and Swiss cheeses (Samelis et al., 2005). The substantial number of surviving LAB can subsequently multiply in the cheese reaching usual levels, similar to what is observed with the application of ionizing radiation (Velasco et al., 2011).

The application of HHP would lead to an increase in the final price of the cheese blocks. The authors do not have data to estimate their price although it has been reported that a newer HHP machine can process over 2000kg/h with a processing cost for solid products of €0.066/kg⁻¹ using 420L vessel (Jung & Tonello-Samson, 2018). Similarly, they have conducted studies on the application of HHP in ready-to-eat (RTE) meat products and, as a point of reference, can provide data on the application of this technology to these products. Equipment from the Hiperbaric brand (HIPERBARIC Europa, Burgos, Spain) has a production capacity of 1000–5000 bags (200g)/hour, depending on the steel vessel capacity, with a price of €0.10–€0.20 per bag. The largest unit of this brand has a vessel of 525L capacity and 380mm diameter, and it can deliver around 3210kg h⁻¹ at 600MPa.

4.3.5.2. Ionizing radiation (IR). Similarly to HHP, food irradiation is a physical, non-thermal processing technology used to kill organisms through the lethal action of IR. Radiation sources for food preservation include gamma rays, electron beams, and X-rays. The FAO/IAEA/WHO Joint Expert Committee established in 1981 that irradiation of food up to an overall dose of 10 kGy is safe (World Health Organization, 1981), and the Codex Alimentarius Commission (Codex Alimentarius Commission, 1984) accepted this as a food standard.

Later, the same international Organisms concluded that any food at any dose is wholesome and safe to consume as long as it remains palatable and maintains its technical properties (World Health Organization, 1999). Despite its high bactericidal effectiveness, the industrial application of this technology is not widespread due to negative connotations associated with the term “radiation”, leading to low consumer acceptance.

The increase in ready-to-eat (RTE) food production in recent decades has led to the application of non-thermal preservation technologies for sanitizing many of these foods. Noted above is the case of HPP to eliminate *L. monocytogenes* from several RTE foods. The IR is an alternative method for this purpose. In fact, many authors have proposed the sanitation of a variety of RTE foods by IR application (Cabeza et al., 2009; Cambero et al., 2012; Cárcel et al., 2015; Munir & Federighi, 2020; Samelis et al., 2005; Tahergorabi et al., 2012).

Considerable knowledge has accumulated regarding the effect of IR on bacteria, with many reviews published on the topic (Ajibola, 2020; Ashraf et al., 2019; Farkas, 2006; Indiarito et al., 2020; Odueke et al., 2016). D-values (dose in kGy to kill 90% of the population) are affected by several factors including temperature (less resistant at room/chill temperatures than at frizzling ones), a_w (the lower the a_w , the higher the resistance), and chemical composition of the food (protein and fat can exert a protective effect) (European Food Safety Authority, 2011). Among bacterial endospores, *C. botulinum*, especially types A and B, has garnered the most interest due to high resistance to irradiation, with reported D-values of 2.2–5.9 kGy (Anellis & Koch, 1962) and 1.3–3.3 kGy (Grecz et al., 1971). Limited studies on the radiation resistance of *Clostridium* spores associated with LBD suggest their relative sensitivity. D-values of 1.5 kGy, 1.77 kGy and 1.5–2.2 kGy have been reported for *C. butyricum* (Losty et al., 1973), *C. tyrobutyricum* (Velasco et al., 2011) and *C. sporogenes* (Farkas, 2006; Losty et al., 1973), respectively.

The application of IR to cheese has been explored by several authors aiming to reduce foodborne pathogens and extend shelf life (Arvanitoyannis & Tserkezou, 2010; Bougle & Stahl, 1994; Hashisaka et al., 1990; Nyamakwere et al., 2022; Odueke et al., 2016; Tsiotsias et al., 2002) achieving favorable results. However, the industrial processing of dairy products using IR has hardly, if ever, been carried out.

To the best of the author’s knowledge, no study has been conducted on the IR application to cheese to minimize LBD, except for the research published

by the authors (Velasco et al., 2011). Their work attempted to reduce *C. tyrobutyricum* spores to negligible levels in RTE pieces of semi-hard cheese. A D-value of 1.77 kGy for *C. tyrobutyricum* spores was determined, and doses of 3 kGy resulted in a 96% spore reduction. Assumptions made by the authors, based on literature data (typical spore concentration in cheese, doubling times of vegetative cells of *C. tyrobutyricum*, required spore number for LBD onset), lead them to the conclusion that the treatment could result in a shelf-life extension of at least 5 months. At doses lower than 3 kGy, the changes in physico-chemical and sensory characteristics of the cheese were negligible but a 3 kGy treatment caused a weak off-odor and off-flavor, although they progressively dissipated during storage (Velasco et al., 2011). The non-permanent intensity in the off-flavour of the irradiated cheese (such as Feta and Ras cheese) has also been reported by several authors (Abd El Baky et al., 1986; Konteles et al., 2009) and its dissipation a few weeks later (Buttery et al., 1973; Kochhar, 1996; Lee & Ahn, 2003). Noteworthy, IR treatment of samples provoked a substantial reduction (3–4 log units) of the indigenous microbiota of cheese, mainly LAB, which was subsequently recovered until reaching the usual levels during the cheese ripening at 14°C (Losty et al., 1973). Therefore, this procedure could be a useful tool to prevent gas production in retail cheese blocks. These products may be potentially contaminated during handling and packaging with microorganisms (pathogen or not) present in the industrial environment. Thus, IR application simultaneously ensures product sanitation because non-sporulating pathogenic bacteria, including the ubiquitous *L. monocytogenes*, are more sensitive to IR (Kim et al., 2017).

Similar considerations to those for HPP may be applied to the economic aspects of the application of ionizing radiation for RTE meat products. The Rhodotron TT200 electron accelerator provides a production throughput of approximately 7000 bags (200g)/hour, with a price of around €0.08 per bag (Data from IONISOS IBERICA, S.A., Tarancón, Cuenca, Spain).

5. Concluding remarks

The clostridial spores withstand pasteurization and they can cause late blowing in semi-hard and hard cheeses. The control of this spoilage remains a challenge for the cheese industry. Several attempts have been made to prevent/minimize LBD based on three strategies: (a) preventing milk contamination on the

farm, (b) removing clostridial spores from raw milk, and (c) applying sporestatic/sporicidal measures to inhibit spore growth or kill them using, respectively, additives (nitrate, lysozyme, antagonist microorganisms) or non-thermal preservation technologies (high hydrostatic pressure and ionizing radiation). Additionally, these technologies could be combined with other procedures to synergistically increase antibacterial action. Although cheese production without blowing defects remains a challenge for the dairy industry, it could be minimized by leveraging methods available through modern food technology.

Authors contributions

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Data availability statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analysed in this study.

References

- Abd El Baky, A. A., Farahat, S. M., Rabie, A. M., & Mobasher, S. A. (1986). The manufacture of Ras cheese from gamma irradiated milk. *Food Chemistry*, 20(3), 201–212. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0308-8146\(86\)90173-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0308-8146(86)90173-1)
- Ajibola, O. J. (2020). An overview of irradiation as a food preservation technique. *Novel Research in Microbiology Journal*, 4, 779–789.
- Alvenas, A. (2015). *Cheese with blowing defect-problematic and preventable methods* [Bachelor Thesis]. Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences.
- Anastasiou, R., Aktypis, A., Georgalaki, M., Papadelli, M., de Vuyst, L., & Tsakalidou, E. (2009). Inhibition of *Clostridium tyrobutyricum* by *Streptococcus macedonicus* ACA-DC 198 under conditions mimicking kasseri cheese production and ripening. *International Dairy Journal*, 19(5), 330–335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.idairyj.2008.12.001>
- Anellis, A., & Koch, R. B. (1962). Comparative resistance of strains of *Clostridium botulinum* spores to gamma rays. *Applied Microbiology*, 10(4), 326–330. <https://doi.org/10.1128/am.10.4.326-330.1962>
- Arias, C., Oliete, B., Seseña, S., Jimenez, L., Pérez-Guzmán, M. D., & Arias, R. (2013). Importance of on-farm management practices on lactate-fermenting *Clostridium* spp. spore contamination of Manchega Ewe milk: Determination of risk factors and characterization of *Clostridium* population. *Small Ruminant Research*, 111(1-3), 120–128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smallrumres.2012.11.030>
- Arvanitoyannis, I., & Tserkezou, P. (2010). Application of irradiation on milk and dairy products. In I. Arvanitoyannis (Ed.), *Irradiation of food commodities* (pp. 265–285). Academic Press.
- Ashraf, S., Sood, M., Bandral, J. D., Trilokia, M., & Manzoor, M. (2019). Food irradiation: A review. *International Journal of Chemical Studies*, 7, 131–136.

- Ávila, M., Gómez-Torres, N., Delgado, D., Gaya, P., & Garde, S. (2016). Application of high pressure processing for controlling *Clostridium tyrobutyricum* and late blowing defect on semi-hard cheese. *Food Microbiology*, 60, 165–173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fm.2016.07.008>
- Ávila, M., Gómez-Torres, N., Gaya, P., & Garde, S. (2020). Effect of a nisin-producing lactococcal starter on the late blowing defect of cheese caused by *Clostridium tyrobutyricum*. *International Journal of Food Science & Technology*, 55(10), 3343–3349. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijfs.14598>
- Ávila, M., Gómez-Torres, N., Hernández, M., & Garde, S. (2014). Inhibitory activity of reuterin, nisin, lysozyme and nitrite against vegetative cells and spores of dairy related *Clostridium* species. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 172, 70–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2013.12.002>
- Ávila, M., Sánchez, C., Calzada, J., Mayer, J. M., Berruga, M., López-Díaz, T. M., Narbad, A., & Garde, S. (2023). Isolation and characterization of new bacteriophages active against *Clostridium tyrobutyricum* and their role in preventing the late blowing defect of cheese. *Food Research International*, 163, 112222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2022.112222>
- Bacci, C., Paris, A., & Brindani, F. (2002). Ruolo di *Clostridium* spp. in Alterazioni del Parmigiano Reggiano Ricongucibili a Gonfiore Tardivo. *Annali Facoltà Medicina*, 22, 221–231.
- Bargeman, G. (2003). Separation technologies to produce dairy ingredients. In G. Smit (Ed.), *Dairy processing: Improving quality* (pp. 366–390). CRC Press.
- Bassi, D., Cappa, F., & Cocconcelli, P. S. (2009). A combination of a SEM technique and X-ray microanalysis for studying the spore germination process of *Clostridium tyrobutyricum*. *Research in Microbiology*, 160(5), 322–329. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resmic.2009.04.003>
- Bassi, D., Puglisi, E., & Cocconcelli, P. S. (2015). Understanding the bacterial communities of hard cheese with blowing defect. *Food Microbiology*, 52, 106–118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fm.2015.07.004>
- Beresford, T. P., Fitzsimons, N. A., Brennan, N. L., & Cogan, T. M. (2001). Recent advances in cheese microbiology. *International Dairy Journal*, 11(4-7), 259–274. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0958-6946\(01\)00056-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0958-6946(01)00056-5)
- Bergère, J., & Favreau, B. (1987). Immuno-Détection des Spores de *Clostridium tyrobutyricum*, Agent du Gonflement Butyrique des Fromages. *Sci Aliments*, 7, 89–98.
- Bergère, J., & Hermier, J. (1970). Spore properties of clostridia occurring in cheese. *The Journal of Applied Bacteriology*, 33(1), 167–179. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2672.1970.tb05242.x>
- Bogovič Matijašić, B., Koman Rajšp, M., Perko, B., & Rogelj, I. (2007). Inhibition of *Clostridium tyrobutyricum* in cheese by *Lactobacillus gasserii*. *International Dairy Journal*, 17(2), 157–166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.idairyj.2006.01.011>
- Borreani, G., Ferrero, F., Nucera, D., Casale, M., Piano, S., & Tabacco, E. (2019). Dairy farm management practices and the risk of contamination of tank milk from *Clostridium* spp. and *Paenibacillus* spp. spores in silage, total mixed ration, dairy cow feces, and raw milk. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 102(9), 8273–8289. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2019-16462>
- Bougle, D. L., & Stahl, V. (1994). Survival of *Listeria monocytogenes* after irradiation treatment of camembert cheeses made from raw milk. *Journal of Food Protection*, 57(9), 811–813. <https://doi.org/10.4315/0362-028X-57.9.811>
- Brändle, J., Domig, K. J., & Kneifel, W. (2016). Relevance and analysis of butyric acid producing clostridia in milk and cheese. *Food Control*, 67, 96–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2016.02.038>
- Brändle, J., Heinzele, L., Fraberger, V., Berta, J., Zitz, U., Schinking, M., Stocker, W., Kneifel, W., & Domig, K. J. (2018). Novel approach to enumerate clostridial endospores in milk. *Food Control*, 85, 318–326. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2017.10.017>
- Breukink, E., & de Kruijff, B. (2006). Lipid II as a target for antibiotics. *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery*, 5(4), 321–332. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrd2004>
- Brown, K. L. (1990). The problems of heat resistant spores in food production. In S. P. Borriello (Ed.), *Clinical and molecular aspects of anaerobes* (pp. 91–101). Wrightson Biomedical.
- Burtscher, J., Hobl, L., Kneifel, W., & Domig, K. J. (2020). Clostridial spore counts in vat milk of alpine dairies. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 103(3), 2111–2116. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2019-17559>
- Burtscher, J., Rudavsky, T., Zitz, U., Neubauer, V., & Domig, K. J. (2023). Importance of pre-milking udder hygiene to reduce transfer of clostridial spores from teat skin to raw milk. *Microorganisms*, 11(5), 1337. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms11051337>
- Buttery, R. C., Guadagni, D. G., & Ling, L. C. (1973). Flavor compounds: Volatilities in vegetable oil and oil water mixture. Estimation of odor thresholds. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 21(2), 198–201. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf60186a029>
- Bylund, G. (2003). *Dairy processing handbook*. Tetra Pak Processing Systems AB.
- Cabeza, M. C., de la Hoz, L., Velasco, R., Cambero, M. I., & Ordóñez, J. A. (2009). Safety and quality of ready-to-eat dry fermented sausages subjected to E-beam radiation. *Meat Science*, 83(2), 320–327. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meatsci.2009.05.019>
- Cambero, M. I., Cabeza, M. C., Escudero, R., Manzano, S., García-Márquez, I., Velasco, R., & Ordóñez, J. A. (2012). Sanitation of selected ready-to-eat intermediate-moisture foods of animal origin by E-beam irradiation. *Foodborne Pathogens and Disease*, 9(7), 594–599. <https://doi.org/10.1089/fpd.2011.1111>
- Cárcel, J. A., Benedito, J., Cambero, M. I., Cabeza, M. C., & Ordóñez, J. A. (2015). Modeling and optimization of the E-beam treatment of chicken steaks and hamburgers, considering food safety, shelf-life, and sensory quality. *Food and Bioprocess Processing*, 96, 133–144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbp.2015.07.006>
- Carminati, D., Bonvini, B., Francolino, S., Ghiglietti, R., Locci, F., Tidona, F., Mariut, M., Abeni, F., Zago, M., & Giraffa, G. (2023). Low-level clostridial spores' milk to limit the onset of late blowing defect in lysozyme-free, grana-type cheese. *Foods*, 12(9), 1880. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12091880>
- Carminati, D., Gatti, M., Bonvini, B., Neviani, E., & Mucchetti, G. (2004). High-pressure processing of gorgonzola cheese: Influence on *Listeria monocytogenes* inactivation and on sensory characteristics. *Journal of Food Protection*, 67(8), 1671–1675. <https://doi.org/10.4315/0362-028X-67.8.1671>
- Cerf, O., Bergere, J.-L., & Hermier, J. (1967). Thermorésistance des Spores de *Clostridium tyrobutyricum* et *Clostridium butyricum*. *Journal of Dairy Research*, 34(3), 221–229. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022029900012395>

- Chen, H., & Hoover, D. (2003). Bacteriocins and their food applications. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*, 2(3), 82–100. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1541-4337.2003.tb00016.x>
- Cocolin, L., Innocente, N., Biasutti, M., & Comi, G. (2004). The late blowing in cheese: A New molecular approach based on PCR and DGGE to study the microbial ecology of the alteration process. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 90(1), 83–91. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605\(03\)00296-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605(03)00296-4)
- Codex Alimentarius Commission. (1984). *Codex general standard for irradiated foods and recommended international code of practice for the operation of radiation facilities used in the treatment of foods* (Vol. 15). Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO).
- Cotter, P. D., Ross, R. P., & Hill, C. (2013). Bacteriocins—A viable alternative to antibiotics? *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, 11(2), 95–105. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrmicro2937>
- Coulon, J. B., Varignier, M., & Darne, D. (1991). Contamination Butyrique du Lait de Vache: Étude dans les Exploitations de Haute-Loire. *INRAE Productions Animales*, 4(5), 369–372. <https://doi.org/10.20870/productions-animales.1991.4.5.4350>
- Cruz-Morales, P., Orellana, C. A., Moutafis, G., Moonen, G., Rincon, G., Nielsen, L. K., & Marcellin, E. (2019). Revisiting the evolution and taxonomy of clostridia, a phylogenomic update. *Genome Biology and Evolution*, 11(7), 2035–2044. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gbe/evz096>
- D'Amico, D. J. (2014). Microbiological quality and safety issues in cheesemaking. *Microbiology Spectrum*, 2(1):CM-0011-2012. Mismatch] <https://doi.org/10.1128/microbiolspec.CM-0011-2012>
- D'Amico, D. J. (2017). Recommendations and outcomes from the first artisan cheese food safety forum. *Food Protection Trends*, 37, 332–339.
- D'Incecco, P., Gatti, M., Hogenboom, J. A., Bottari, B., Rosi, V., Neviani, E., & Pellegrino, L. (2016). Lysozyme affects the microbial catabolism of free arginine in raw milk hard cheeses. *Food Microbiology*, 57, 16–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fm.2015.11.020>
- D'Incecco, P., Pellegrino, L., Hogenboom, J. A., Sandro, P., & Bassi, D. (2018). The Late Blowing defect of hard cheeses: Behaviour of cells and spores of *Clostridium tyrobutyricum* throughout the cheese manufacturing and ripening. *LWT*, 87, 134–141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2017.08.083>
- Daly, D. F. M., McSweeney, P. L. H., & Sheehan, J. J. (2010). Split defect and secondary fermentation in Swiss-type cheeses – A review. *Dairy Science & Technology*, 90(1), 3–26. <https://doi.org/10.1051/dst/2009036>
- Deiana, P., Fatichenti, F., Farris, G. A., Mocquot, P., Lodi, R., Todesco, R., & Cecchi, L. (1984). Metabolization of lactic and acetic acids in pecorino romano cheese made with a combined starter of lactic acid bacteria and yeast. *Le Lait*, 64(640-642), 380–394. <https://doi.org/10.1051/lait:1984640-64231>
- del Rio, B., Sánchez-Llana, E., Redruello, B., Magadan, A. H., Fernández, M., Martín, M. C., Ladero, V., & Alvarez, M. A. (2019). *Enterococcus faecalis* bacteriophage 156 is an effective biotechnological tool for reducing the presence of tyramine and putrescine in an experimental cheese model. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 10, 566. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2019.00566>
- Demarquilly, C. (2020). Ensilage et contamination du lait par les spores butyriques. *Inrae Productions Animales*, 11(5), 359–364. <https://doi.org/10.20870/productions-animales.1998.11.5.3964>
- Di Cagno, R., Gobbetti, M., & Cheese. (2001). Hard Italian cheeses. In J. W. Fuquay (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of dairy sciences* (2nd ed., pp. 378–385). Elsevier.
- Driehuis, F. (2013). Silage and the safety and quality of dairy foods: A review. *Agricultural and Food Science*, 22(1), 16–34. <https://doi.org/10.23986/afsci.6699>
- Driehuis, F., & Elferink, S. O. (2000). The impact of the quality of silage on animal health and food safety: A review. *Veterinary Quarterly*, 22(4), 212–216. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01652176.2000.9695061>
- Düsterhöft, E. M., Engels, W., Huppertz, T., McSweeney, P. L. H., Fox, P. F., & Cotter, P. D. (2017). Gouda and related cheeses. In D. W. Everett (Eds.), *Cheese: Chemistry, physics and microbiology* (pp. 103–140). Academic Press.
- Düsterhöft, E. M., & Van den Berg, G. (2007). How may late blowing be avoided in gouda-type cheeses? In P. L. H. McSweeney (Ed.), *Cheese problems solved* (pp. 242–243). Woodhead.
- Egan, K., Field, D., Rea, M. C., Ross, R. P., Hill, C., & Cotte, P. D. (2016). Bacteriocins: Novel solutions to age old spore-related problems? *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 7, 461. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2016.00461>
- El Haddad, L., Roy, J. P., Khalil, G. E., St-Gelais, D., Champagne, C. P., Labrie, S., & Moineau, S. (2016). Efficacy of two *Staphylococcus aureus* phage cocktails in cheese production. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 217, 7–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2015.10.001>
- European Food Safety Authority. (2011). Scientific opinion on the efficacy and microbiological safety of irradiation of food. *EFSA Journal*, 9, 2103.
- European Food Safety Authority. (2014). Scientific opinion on the evaluation of allergenic foods and food ingredients for labelling purposes. *EFSA Journal*, 12, 3894.
- Farkas, J. (2006). Irradiation for better foods. *Trends in Food Science and Technology*, 17(4), 148–152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2005.12.003>
- FDA. (2024). Pasteurized milk ordinance centennial. <https://www.fda.gov/food/milk-guidance-documents-regulatory-information/pasteurized-milk-ordinance-centennial>
- Feligini, M., Brambati, E., Panelli, S., Ghitti, M., Sacchi, R., Capelli, E., & Bonacina, C. (2014). One-year investigation of *Clostridium* spp. occurrence in raw milk and curd of Grana Padano cheese by the automated ribosomal intergenic spacer analysis. *Food Control*, 42, 71–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2014.02.002>
- Fox, P. F., Guinee, T. P., Cogan, T. M., & McSweeney, P. L. H. (2017). Microbiology of cheese ripening. In P. F. Fox, T. P. Guinee, T. M. Cogan, & P. L. H. McSweeney, (Eds.), *Fundamentals of cheese science* (pp. 333–390). Springer.
- Fröhlich-Wyder, M. T., & Bachmann, H. P. (2007). What causes irregular eye formation, splits or cracks in Emmental cheese? In P. L. H. McSweeney (Ed.), *Cheese problems solved* (pp. 252–253). Woodhead.
- Fryer, T. F., & Halligan, A. C. (1976). The detection of *Clostridium tyrobutyricum* in milk. *N. Journal of Dairy Science and Technology*, 11, 132.
- Garde, S., Arias, R., Gaya, P., & Nuñez, M. (2011). Occurrence of *Clostridium* spp. in ovine milk and Manchego cheese

- with late blowing defect: Identification and characterization of isolates. *International Dairy Journal*, 21(4), 272–278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.idairyj.2010.11.003>
- Garriga, M., Grèbol, N., Aymerich, M. T., Monfort, J. M., & Hugas, M. (2004). Microbial inactivation after high-pressure processing at 600 Mpa in commercial meat products over its shelf life. *Innovative Food Science and Emerging Technologies*, 5(4), 451–457. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifset.2004.07.001>
- Georget, E., Sevenich, R., Reineke, K., Mathys, A., Heinz, V., Callanan, M., Rauh, C., & Knorr, C. (2015). Inactivation of microorganisms by high isostatic pressure processing in complex matrices: A review. *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, 27, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifset.2014.10.015>
- Gésan-Guiziou, G. (2010). Removal of bacteria, spores and somatic cells from milk by centrifugation and microfiltration techniques. In M. W. Griffiths (Ed.), *Improving the safety and quality of milk* (pp. 349–372). Woodhead.
- Ghoddusi, H. B., Sherburn, R. E., & Aboaba, O. O. (2013). Growth Limiting pH, water activity, and temperature for neurotoxicogenic strains of *Clostridium butyricum*. *ISRN Microbiology*, 2013, 731430. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2013/731430>
- Gobbeti, M. (2004). Extra-hard varieties. In P. F. Fox, T. P. Guinee, T. M. Cogan, & P. L. H. McSweeney (Eds.), *Cheese: Chemistry, physics and microbiology* (3rd ed., Vol. 2, pp. 51–70). Elsevier Academic Press.
- Gobbetti, M., & Di Cagno, R. (2007). What common problems are associated with grana-type cheeses? In P. L. H. McSweeney (Ed.), *Cheese problems solved* (pp. 210–211). Woodhead.
- Gómez-Torres, N., Ávila, M., Gaya, P., & Garde, S. (2014). Prevention of late blowing defect by Reuterin produced in cheese by a *Lactobacillus reuteri* adjunct. *Food Microbiology*, 42, 82–88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fm.2014.02.018>
- González, L., & Zárate, V. (2015). Inhibitory activity of *Lactobacillus plantarum* TF711 against *Clostridium sporogenes* when used as adjunct culture in cheese manufacture. *The Journal of Dairy Research*, 82(2), 236–241. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022029915000126>
- Goulding, D. A., Fox, P. F., & O'Mahony, J. A. (2019). Milk proteins: An overview. In M. Boland, & H. Singh (Eds.), *Milk proteins: From expression to food* (pp. 21–98). Elsevier Applied Science.
- Grecz, N., Walker, A. A., Anellis, A., & Berkowitz, D. (1971). Effect of irradiation temperature in the range -196 to 95°C on the resistance of *Clostridium botulinum*. *Canadian Journal of Microbiology*, 17(2), 135–142. <https://doi.org/10.1139/m71-024>
- Gudbjornsdottir, B., Jonsson, A., Hafsteinsson, H., & Heinz, V. (2010). Effect of high pressure processing on *Listeria* spp. and on the textural and microstructural properties of cold smoked salmon. *LWT*, 43(2), 366–374. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2009.08.015>
- Guinee, T. P., & Fox, P. F. (2017). Salt in cheese: Physical, chemical and biological aspects. In P. L. H. McSweeney, P. F. Fox, P. D. Cotter, & D. W. Everett (Eds.), *Cheese: Chemistry, physics and microbiology* (pp. 317–375). Academic Press.
- Guinee, T. P., & O'Callaghan, D. J. (2010). Control and prediction of quality characteristics in the manufacture and ripening of cheese. In B. A. Law, A. Y. Tamime (Eds.), *Technology of cheesemaking* (2nd ed., pp. 260–329). Wiley-Blackwell.
- Hashisaka, A. E., Matches, J. R., Batters, Y., Hungate, F. P., & Dong, F. M. (1990). Effects of gamma radiation at -78°C on microbial populations in dairy products. *Journal of Food Science*, 55(5), 1284–1289. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2621.1990.tb03917.x>
- Hassan, H., St-Gelais, D., Gomaa, A., & Fliss, I. (2021). Impact of nisin and nisin-producing *Lactococcus lactis* ssp. *lactis* on *Clostridium tyrobutyricum* and bacterial ecosystem of cheese matrices. *Foods*, 10(4), 898. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods10040898>
- Heyndrickx, M. (2011). The importance of endospore-forming bacteria originating from soil for contamination of industrial food processing. *Applied and Environmental Soil Science*, 2011, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2011/561975>
- Hill, A. R., & Kethireddipalli, P. (2013). Dairy products: Cheese and yoghurt. In N. A. M. Eskin, & F. Shahidi (Eds.), *Biochemistry of foods* (pp. 319–351). Academic Press.
- Huchet, V., Thuault, D., & Bourgeois, C. M. (1995). Modélisation des Effets du pH, de l'Acide Lactique, du Glycérol et du NaCl sur la Croissance des Cellules Végétatives de *Clostridium tyrobutyricum* en Milieu de Culture. *Le Lait*, 75(6), 585–593. <https://doi.org/10.1051/lait:1995645>
- Hunter, J., & Frazier, W. C. (1961). Gas production by associated Swiss cheese bacteria. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 44(12), 2176–2186. [https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302\(61\)90044-3](https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(61)90044-3)
- Indiarto, R., Pratama, A. W., Theodora, H., C., & Sari, T. I. (2020). Food irradiation technology: A review of the uses and their capabilities. *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology*, 68(12), 91–98. <https://doi.org/10.14445/22315381/IJETT-V68I12P216>
- Ingham, S. C., Hassler, J. R., Tsai, Y. W., & Ingham, B. H. (1998). Differentiation of lactate-fermenting, gas-producing *Clostridium* spp. isolated from milk. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 43(3), 173–183. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605\(98\)00108-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605(98)00108-1)
- Jung, S., & Tonello-Samson, C. M. (2018). High hydrostatic pressure food processing: Potential and limitations. In A. Proctor (Ed.), *Alternatives to conventional food processing* (2nd ed., pp. 251–315). Royal Society of Chemistry.
- Kaya, H. I., Simsek, O., & Akgunoglu, O. (2023). Diversity of *Clostridium* spp. causing late blowing in Kaşar cheese and their behaviour against various antimicrobials. *International Dairy Journal*, 139, 105560. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.idairyj.2022.105560>
- Kim, H. J., Song, B. S., Kim, J. H., Choi, J., Lee, J. W., Byun, M. W., & Jo, C. R. (2017). Application of gamma irradiation for the microbiological safety of sliced cheddar cheese. *Journal of Radiation Industry*, 1, 15–19.
- Klantschitsch, T. (1999). *Influence of microfiltration on the quality of semi-hard cheese from raw milk with particular emphasis on Clostridium tyrobutyricum spores* [Doctoral Thesis]. Swiss Federal Institute of Technology (ETH).
- Klijn, N., Nieuwenhof, F. F. J., Hoolwerf, J. D., van der Waals, C. B., & Weerkamp, A. H. (1995). Identification of *Clostridium tyrobutyricum* as the causative agent of late blowing in cheese by species-specific PCR amplification. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 61(8), 2919–2924. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aem.61.8.2919-2924.1995>

- Kochhar, S. P. (1996). Oxidation pathways to the formation of off-flavours. In M. J. Saxby (Ed.), *Food taints and off-flavours* (2nd ed., pp. 168–225). Blackie Academic & Professional.
- Konteles, S., Sinanoglou, V. J., Batrinou, A., & Sflomos, K. (2009). Effects of g-irradiation on *Listeria monocytogenes* population, colour, texture and sensory properties of Feta cheese during cold storage. *Food Microbiology*, 26(2), 157–165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fm.2008.10.006>
- Le Bourhis, A. G., Doré, J., Carlier, J. P., Chamba, J. F., Popoff, M. R., & Tholozan, J. L. (2007). Contribution of *C. beijerinckii* and *C. sporogenes* in Association with *C. tyrobutyricum* to the butyric fermentation in Emmental type cheese. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 113(2), 154–163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2006.06.027>
- Le Bourhis, A. G., Saunier, K., Doré, J., Carlier, J. P., Chamba, J. F., Popoff, M. R., & Tholozan, J. L. (2005). Development and validation of PCR primers to assess the diversity of *Clostridium* spp. in cheese by temporal temperature gradient gel electrophoresis. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 71(1), 29–38. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.71.1.29-38.2005>
- Lecote, N., Fauquant, J., Robert, B., Beaucher, E., Rousseau, F., Sinet, C., Camier, B., Madec, M. N., Tanguy-Sai, G., & Lopez, C. (2014). Procédé Combinant l'homogénéisation et la Microfiltration Tangentielle pour Réduire la Teneur Bactérienne de Lait Contenant de la Matière Grasse. Presented at the MEMPRO V, Toulouse, France. Lavoisier Technique et Documentation: Toulouse (p. 105).
- Lee, E. J., & Ahn, D. U. (2003). Production of volatiles from fatty acids and oils by irradiation. *Journal of Food Science*, 68(1), 70–75. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2621.2003.tb14116.x>
- Lembke, F., & Teuber, M. (1981). Anaerobe Sporenbildner in der Milch und deren Eliminierbarkeit Durch Zentrifugalverfahren. *Molkerei-Ztg. Welt der Milch*, 35, 871–873.
- Librán, C. M., Moro, A., Zalacain, A., Molina, A., Carmona, M., & Berruga, M. I. (2013). Potential application of aromatic plant extracts to prevent cheese blowing. *World Journal of Microbiology & Biotechnology*, 29(7), 1179–1188. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11274-013-1280-x>
- Losty, T., Roth, J. S., & Shults, G. (1973). Effect of gamma-irradiation and heating on proteolytic activity of meat samples. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 21(2), 275–277. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf60186a016>
- Marcos, A., Alcalá, M., León, F., Fernández-Salguero, J., & Esteban, M. A. (1981). Water activity and chemical composition of cheese. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 64(4), 622–626. [https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302\(81\)82621-5](https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(81)82621-5)
- Martínez-Cuesta, M. C., Bengoechea, J., Bustos, I., Rodríguez, B., Requena, T., & Peláez, C. (2010). Control of late blowing in cheese by adding Lacticin 3147-producing *Lactococcus lactis* IFPL 3593 to the starter. *International Dairy Journal*, 20(1), 18–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.idairyj.2009.07.005>
- Martínez-Rodríguez, Y., Acosta-Muñiz, C., Olivas, G. I., Guerrero-Beltrán, J., Rodrigo-Aliaga, D., & Sepúlveda, D. R. (2012). High hydrostatic pressure processing of cheese. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*, 11(4), 399–416. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1541-4337.2012.00192.x>
- Mathot, A. G., Beliard, E., & Thuault, D. (2003). *Streptococcus thermophilus* 580 produces a bacteriocin potentially suitable for inhibition of *Clostridium tyrobutyricum* in hard cheese. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 86(10), 3068–3074. [https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302\(03\)73906-X](https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(03)73906-X)
- Matteuzzi, D., Trovatelli, L. D., Biavati, B., & Zani, G. (1977). Clostridia from Grana cheese. *Journal of Applied Bacteriology*, 43(3), 375–382. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2672.1977.tb00763.x>
- McSweeney, P. L. H., & Fox, P. F. (2004). Metabolism of residual lactose and of lactate and citrate. In P. F. Fox, T. P. Guinee, T. M. Cogan, & P. L. H. McSweeney (Eds.), *Cheese: Chemistry, physics and microbiology* (3rd ed., Vol. 1, pp. 361–371). Elsevier Academic Press.
- Metlitskaya, A., Kazakov, T., Kommer, A., Pavlova, O., Praetorius-Ibba, M., Ibba, M., Krashennikov, I., Kolb, V., Khmel, I., & Severinov, K. (2006). Aspartyl-tRNA synthetase is the target of peptide nucleotide antibiotic microcin C. *The Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 281(26), 18033–18042. <https://doi.org/10.1074/jbc.M513174200>
- Modi, R., Hirvi, Y., Hill, A., & Griffiths, M. (2001). Effect of phage on survival of *Salmonella enteritidis* during manufacture and storage of cheddar cheese made from raw and pasteurized milk. *Journal of Food Protection*, 64(7), 927–933. <https://doi.org/10.4315/0362-028x-64.7.927>
- Montiel, R., Bravo, D., de Alba, M., Gaya, P., & Medina, M. (2012). Combined effect of high pressure treatment and the lactoperoxidase system on the inactivation of *Listeria monocytogenes* in cold-smoked salmon. *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, 16, 26–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifset.2012.03.005>
- Morandi, S., Battelli, G., Silveti, T., Tringali, S., Nunziata, L., Villa, A., Acquistapace, A., & Brasca, M. (2021). Impact of salting and ripening temperatures on late blowing defect in Valtellina Casera PDO cheese. *Food Control*, 120, 107508. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2020.107508>
- Mota, M. J., Lopes, R. P., Delgadillo, I., & Saraiva, J. A. (2013). Microorganisms under high pressure: Adaptation, growth and biotechnological potential. *Biotechnology Advances*, 31(8), 1426–1434. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotechadv.2013.06.007>
- Mullan, W. M. A. (1986). Bacteriophage induced starter problems. *Dairy Industries International*, 51, 40–43.
- Mullan, W. M. A. (2000). Causes and control of early gas production in cheddar cheese. *International Journal of Dairy Technology*, 53(2), 63–68. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-0307.2000.tb02660.x>
- Munir, M. T., & Federighi, M. (2020). Control of foodborne biological hazards by ionizing radiations. *Foods*, 9(7), 878. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9070878>
- Myers, K., Cannon, J., Montoya, D., Dickson, J., Lonergan, S., & Sebranek, J. (2013). Effects of high hydrostatic pressure and varying concentrations of sodium nitrite from traditional and vegetable-based sources on the growth of *Listeria monocytogenes* on ready-to-eat (RTE) sliced ham. *Meat Science*, 94(1), 69–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meatsci.2012.12.019>
- Nyamakwere, F., Esposito, G., Dzama, K., Gouws, P., Rapisarda, T., Belvedere, G., Masucci, F., & Raffrenato, E. (2022). Application of gamma irradiation treatment on the physicochemical and microbiological quality of an artisanal hard cheese. *Applied Sciences*, 12(6), 3142. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12063142>

- O'Reilly, C. E., Kelly, A. L., Oliveira, J. C., Murphy, P. M., Auty, M. A. E., & Beresford, T. P. (2003). Effect of varying high-pressure treatment conditions on acceleration of ripening of cheddar cheese. *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, 4(3), 277–284. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1466-8564\(03\)00037-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1466-8564(03)00037-7)
- O'Sullivan, D. J., Giblin, L., Paul, L. H., McSweeney, P. L. H., Sheehan, J. J., & Cotter, P. D. (2013). Nucleic Acid-based Approaches to Investigate Microbial-related Cheese Quality Defects. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 4, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2013.00001>
- Odueke, O. B., Farag, K. W., Baines, R. N., & Chadd, S. A. (2016). Irradiation applications in dairy products: A review. *Food and Bioprocess Technology*, 9(5), 751–767. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11947-016-1709-y>
- Oliveira, R. B. A., Margalho, L. P., Nascimento, J. S., Costa, L. E. O., Portela, J. B., Cruz, A. G., & Sant'Ana, A. S. (2016). Processed cheese contamination by spore-forming bacteria: A review of sources, routes, fate during processing and control. *Trends in Food Science and Technology*, 57, 11–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2016.09.008>
- Parks, W., Bottrill, A. R., Pierrat, O. A., Durrant, M. C., & Maxwell, A. (2007). The Action of the Bacterial Toxin, Microcin B17, on DNA Gyrase. *Biochimie*, 89(4), 500–507. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biochi.2006.12.005>
- Piot, M., Vachot, J. C., Veaux, M., Maubois, J. L., & Brinkman, G. E. (1987). Ecrémage et Épuration Bactérienne du Lait Entier Cru par Microfiltration sur Membrane en Flux Tangentiel. *Tech. Lait. Mark*, 1016, 42–46.
- Pirisi, A., Lauret, A., & Dubeuf, J. P. (2007). Basic and incentive payments for goat and sheep milk in relation to quality. *Small Ruminant Research*, 68(1-2), 167–178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smallrumres.2006.09.009>
- Podrzaj, L., Burtcher, J., Küller, F., & Domig, K. J. (2020). Strain-dependent cheese spoilage potential of *Clostridium tyrobutyricum*. *Microorganisms*, 8(11), 1836. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8111836>
- Qian, C., Martin, N. H., Wiedmann, M., & Trmčić, A. (2022). Development of a risk assessment model to predict the occurrence of late blowing defect in gouda cheese and evaluate potential intervention strategies. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 105(4), 2880–2894. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2021-21206>
- Ramos-Vivas, J., Elexpuru-Zabaleta, M., Samano, M. L., Barrera, A. P., Forbes-Hernández, T. Y., Giampieri, F., & Battino, M. (2021). Phages and enzybiotics in food bio-preservation. *Molecules*, 26(17), 5138. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26175138>
- Rubio, B., Martínez, B., García-Cachán, M. D., Rovira, J., & Jaime, I. (2007). Effect of high pressure preservation on the quality of dry cured beef “Cecina de Leon”. *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, 8(1), 102–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifset.2006.08.004>
- Salmerón, J., de Vega, C., Pérez-Elortondo, F. J., Albisu, M., & Barrón, L. J. R. (2002). Effect of pasteurization and seasonal variations in the microflora of Ewe's milk for cheese-making. *Food Microbiology*, 19(2-3), 167–174. <https://doi.org/10.1006/fmic.2001.0475>
- Samelis, J., Kakouri, A., Savvaidis, I. N., Riganakos, K., & Kontominas, M. G. (2005). Use of ionizing radiation doses of 2 and 4 kGy to control *Listeria* spp. and *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 on frozen meat trimmings used for dry fermented sausage production. *Meat Science*, 70(1), 189–195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meatsci.2005.01.002>
- Sanjuán, E., Millán, R., Saavedra, P., Carmona, M. A., Gómez, R., & Fernández-Salguero, J. (2002). Influence of animal and vegetable rennet on the physicochemical characteristics of los pedroches cheese during ripening. *Food Chemistry*, 78(3), 281–289. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0308-8146\(02\)00098-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0308-8146(02)00098-5)
- Scintu, M. F., Mannu, L., & Caria, A. (2004). Presence of spores of *Clostridium* spp. in Ewes' raw milk. *International Dairy Federation*, 3, 187.
- Shao, Y., Ramaswamy, H. S., & Zhu, S. (2007). High-pressure destruction kinetics of spoilage and pathogenic bacteria in raw milk cheese. *Journal of Food Process Engineering*, 30(3), 357–374. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-4530.2007.00114.x>
- Sheehan, J. J. C. (2022). Avoidance of gas blowing. In P. L. H. McSweeney, & J. P. McNamara (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of dairy science* (3rd ed., pp. 15–21). Academic Press.
- Shi, X., Qian, C., Murphy, S. I., Wiedmann, M., & Martin, N. H. (2023). Butyric acid-producing bacterial spore levels in conventional raw milk vary by farm. *JDS Communications*, 4(1), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jdsc.2022-0252>
- Silva, C. C. G., Silva, S. P. M., & Ribeiro, S. C. (2018). Application of bacteriocins and protective cultures in dairy food preservation. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 9, 594. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2018.00594>
- Silvetti, T., Morandi, S., Hintersteiner, M., & Brasca, M. (2017). Use of hen egg white lysozyme in the food industry. In P. Y. Hester (Ed.), *Egg innovations and strategies for improvements* (pp. 233–242). Elsevier Academic Press.
- Simonart, P. D., & Beer, G. (1953). Recherches en vue d'améliorer la qualité microbiologique des laits par ultracentrifugation. *Netherland Milk and Dairy Journal*, 7, 117–128.
- Stadhouders, J., & Jørgensen, K. (1990). Prevention of the contamination of raw milk by a hygienic milk production. *Bulletin of the International Dairy Federation*, 251, 32–36.
- Su, Y. C., & Ingham, S. C. (2000). Influence of milk centrifugation, brining and ripening conditions in preventing gas formation by *Clostridium* spp. in Gouda cheese. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 54(3), 147–154. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605\(99\)00199-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1605(99)00199-3)
- Tabla, R., Gómez, A., Rebollo, J. E., Molina, F., & Roa, I. (2022). Effectiveness of a bacteriophage cocktail in reducing cheese early blowing caused by *Escherichia coli*. *LWT*, 153, 112430. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2021.112430>
- Tahergorabi, R., Matak, K. E., & Jaczynski, J. (2012). Application of electron beam to inactivate salmonella in food: Recent developments. *Food Research International*, 45(2), 685–694. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2011.02.003>
- Tsiotsias, A., Savvaidis, I., Vassila, A., Kontominas, M., & Kotzekidou, P. (2002). Control of *Listeria monocytogenes* by low-dose irradiation in combination with refrigeration in the soft whey cheese anthotyros. *Food Microbiology*, 19(2-3), 117–126. <https://doi.org/10.1006/fmic.2001.0469>
- Turchi, B., Pero, S., Torracca, B., Fratini, F., Mancini, S., Galiero, A., Pedonese, F., Nuvoloni, R., & Cerri, D. (2016). Occurrence of *Clostridium* spp. in Ewe's milk: Enumeration and identification of isolates. *Dairy Science & Technology*, 96(5), 693–701. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13594-016-0298-x>
- Van den Berg, G., Meijer, W. C., Düsterhöft, E. M., Smit, G., Fox, P. F., Guinee, T. P., & Cogan, T. M. (2004). Gouda and

- related cheeses. In P. L. H. McSweeney (Eds.), *Cheese: Chemistry, physics and microbiology* (3rd ed., Vol. 2, pp 103–140). Elsevier Academic Press.
- Velasco, R., Ordóñez, J. A., Cabeza, M. C., de la Hoz, L., & Cambero, M. I. (2011). Use of the E-beam radiation to diminish the late blowing of cheese. *International Dairy Journal*, 21(7), 493–500. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.idairyj.2011.01.011>
- Vikram, A., Woolston, J., & Sulakvelidze, A. (2021). Phage biocontrol applications in food production and processing. *Current Issues in Molecular Biology*, 40, 267–302. <https://doi.org/10.21775/cimb.040.267>
- Vincent, P. A., & Morero, R. D. (2009). The structure and biological aspects of peptide antibiotic microcin J25. *Current Medicinal Chemistry*, 16(5), 538–549. <https://doi.org/10.2174/092986709787458461>
- Vissers, M. M. M., Driehuis, F., Te Giffel, M. C., De Jong, P., & Lankveld, J. M. G. (2007). Minimizing the level of butyric acid bacteria spores in farm tank milk. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 90(7), 3278–3285. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2006-798>
- Waes, G., & Heddeghem, A. (1990). Prevention of butyric acid fermentation by bacterial centrifugation of the cheese milk. *Bull. Int. Dairy Fed*, 251, 47–50.
- Walstra, P., Noomen, A., & Geurts, T. J. (1999). Dutch-type varieties. In P. F. Fox (Ed.), *Cheese: Chemistry, physics and microbiology* (2nd ed., Vol. 2, pp. 79–82). Aspen Publishers.
- Wang, C. Y., Huang, H. W., Hsu, C. P., & Yang, B. B. (2016). Recent advances in food processing using high hydrostatic pressure technology. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 56(4), 527–540. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2012.745479>
- Wang, Y., Wu, J., Lv, M., Shao, Z., Hungwe, M., Wang, J., Bai, X., Xie, J., Wang, Y., & Geng, W. (2021). Metabolism characteristics of lactic acid bacteria and the expanding applications in food industry. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 9, 612285. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2021.612285>
- Wasserfall, F., & Teuber, M. (1979). Action of egg white lysozyme on *Clostridium tyrobutyricum*. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 38(2), 197–199. <https://doi.org/10.1128/aem.38.2.197-199.1979>
- Wieringa, G. W. (1958). The effect of wilting on butyric acid fermentation in silage. *Netherlands Journal of Agricultural Science*, 6(3), 204–210. <https://doi.org/10.18174/njas.v6i3.17706>
- Wijayanti, H. B., Bansal, N., & Deeth, H. C. (2014). Stability of whey proteins during thermal processing: A review. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*, 13(6), 1235–1251. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.12105>
- World Health Organization. (1981). *Wholesomeness of irradiated food. Report of a Joint FAO/IAEA/WHO Expert Committee*. WHO.
- World Health Organization. (1999). *High-dose irradiation: Wholesomeness of food irradiated with doses above 10 kGy: Report of a Joint FAO/IAEA/WHO Study Group*. WHO.
- Zhang, H., Fu, G., & Zhang, D. (2014). Cloning, characterization, and production of a novel lysozyme by different expression hosts. *Journal of Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 24(10), 1405–1412. <https://doi.org/10.4014/jmb.1404.04039>
- Zucali, M., Bava, L., Colombini, S., Brasca, M., Decimo, M., Morandi, S., Tamburini, A., & Crovetto, G. M. (2015). Management practices and forage quality affecting the contamination of milk with anaerobic spore-forming bacteria. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 95(6), 1294–1302. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.6822>